

Impact of Organizational Culture and Work Environment on Occupational Health and Safety, Mediated by Work Motivation (At PT Manunggal Jaya Makmur)

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Abstract:- This study at PT Manunggal Jaya Makmur intends to examine the effects of organizational culture and work environment on workers' occupational safety and health using work motivation as a mediating variable. All employees make up the study's population, which included a sample size of 50 people. The Structural Equation Model-Partial Least Square (SEM-PLS) data analysis technique is used. Based on the findings of the study and the discussion, it can be said that organizational culture affects occupational safety and health in a positive and significant way. This indicates that increasing organizational culture's level of self-awareness will improve occupational safety and health. A strong company culture will boost employee motivation since it has a favorable, significant impact on job motivation. The working environment has a positive and significant impact on occupational safety and health, therefore working conditions in terms of employee interactions, specifically employee cooperation, have an effect on enhancing occupational safety and health. A good work environment will influence employee work motivation since the work environment has a positive and significant impact on it. Workplace safety and health are dramatically improved by work motivation. Workplace safety and health will both rise dramatically with a strong organizational culture. Workplace harmony will greatly boost safety and health at work as well as employee motivation.

Keywords:- Occupational Safety and Health (OSH), Work Motivation, Organizational Culture.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human resources are crucial to any organization, including businesses and organizations, and they cannot even be separated from them. They are also the primary factor in determining how a firm will develop. In order for employees to perform jobs effectively and efficiently and help the firm accomplish its goals, human resource management (HRM) is the first stage in developing quality human resources for businesses. Although occupational safety and health are two distinct concepts in practice, they are always brought together and discussed at the same time in human resource management. If an occupational safety and health program

can be effectively conveyed by the employer to all workers participating in the work, it will be successful.

Table 1. Accident data involving PT Manunggal Jaya Makmur employees

Year	Number of Work Accidents Per Years	Information
2019	8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 70% Poor work ethic due to lack of SOP • 30% Poor work environment and irregular machine maintenance
2020	5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 60% Failed to follow specified work SOP guidelines • 20% Poor work environment and irregular machine maintenance • 20% of the Time, Poor Weather
2021	3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3 • 50% Does not adhere to the work SOP's specified requirements • 20% Poor work environment and irregular machine maintenance 30% Unfavorable Weather
Amount	16	

PT Manunggal Java Makmur is the source.

According to Table 1 of 2019, up to 70% of accidents are the result of poor work discipline on the part of employees since the organization did not create effective SOPs for them to follow. The organization's management put together corporate SOPs at the end of 2019 to lessen the effects of workplace accidents, including the registration of BPJS Health and BPJS Employment. 2020 shows a reduction in work accidents from 70% to 60%, with a majority of these accidents being brought on by workers' negligence in failing to follow established SOP rules. Additionally, 20% of work accidents are brought on by erratic machine maintenance checks and an unfavorable work environment, and 20% are brought on by unforeseen and uncontrollable bad weather conditions. Because the business has put the proper SOP in place for its employees, you can see that the statistic for 2021 indicates that 50% of workplace accidents caused by negligence are declining every year.

One of the businesses in the Tangerang region offering cargo services is PT Manunggal Jaya Makmur. In order to implement an organizational culture with good discipline at work, the company must be able to make the appropriate SOP

and supervise its employees. The company must also regularly check the work environment to see if there are issues between employees as well as check for maintenance. to lessen how negatively work accidents impair workers' ability to operate. The issue the company is currently dealing with is a result of a decline in organizational culture, specifically the lack of work discipline among employees who are influenced by themselves and unfavorable workplace variables that affect these employees' safety and risk of workplace accidents as well as their level of motivation at work. A culture of strong work discipline, appropriate occupational health and safety, and an accommodating work environment are required to stabilize employee motivation.

Elmi (2018) claims that occupational health is a type of health insurance provided to a person while they are working. Elmi (2018) asserts that the primary method for preventing accidents that result in injuries or fatalities at work is workplace safety.

It was determined from earlier studies by Thorvaldsen (2022) and June et al. (2020) that workplace safety and health and environment have a major impact. Based on the study's findings, it was determined how important it is to implement occupational safety and health at work. Because some employees are still unaware of the significance of occupational safety and health, businesses need to pay attention to the workplace environment in order to maintain employee performance. According to Nielsen's (2014) research, corporate culture significantly and favorably affects occupational safety and health. According to Rukhyanti's research findings from 2007, ensuring worker safety is viewed as a component in boosting employee motivation. This is similar to research conducted by Munandarr (2014) because it has been established that occupational health is a factor significantly influencing job motivation. According to the findings of Santoso (2021), the company's safety performance will be better the better the occupational safety and health work program, the factors that lead to work accidents and learning, the culture or work climate, and the occupational safety and health competencies implemented. Occupational safety and health at PT are impacted by the work environment and organizational culture, according to research by Setyowidodo (2022). Rajawali I simultaneously with PG. According to research by Rio, Andini, and Oktafian (2022), work motivation acts as an intermediary variable to mediate the favorable effects of occupational safety and health, work environment, and work discipline on performance. Research findings by Marzuki et al. The formation of organizational culture requires a process of thinking and acting to become safe work habits, takes time, and of course the support of existing management systems so that employees are exposed to work safely, so it is known (as of 2018) that organizational culture does not affect occupational safety and health performance. According to Utami's research from 2017, there is no discernible relationship between workplace safety and employee performance when the work environment acts as an intervening element. Darmawan, Winarno, and Krisnandini's research findings from 2021 demonstrate that work motivation is unable to mitigate the impact of corporate culture and work environment on performance. These studies'

findings revealed certain study gaps in the areas of workplace culture, work environment, and employee motivation for occupational safety and health.

II. READING REVIEW

A. Safety and Health at Work

Mengginson claims that safety encompasses both safety risk and health risk, with the two categories being distinguished in the context of the workplace (Mangkunegara, 2015). While occupational health is a general state of the physical, mental, and emotional well-being of employees where they work, according to Mathis and Jackson (2009), work safety is a condition in which the physical well-being of employees is protected.

B. Company's Culture

Organizational culture, according to Mangkunegara (2016), is a set of presumptions or a system of beliefs, values, and norms formed within the company that serves as a model for how its members should behave in order to overcome external adaption and internal integration.

C. Environment at work

The work environment, according to Sedarmayanti (2017), consists of all the equipment and supplies used, the surroundings where a person works, his work processes, and his work arrangements both individually and as a group.

D. Motivation at work

Wibowo (2016) proposes that goal-oriented behavior can be used to characterize job motivation. Workplace encouragement and excitement are produced through work motivation (Sedarmayanti, 2018).

E. Framework

Image 1. Thinking Process

Hypothesis:

- H1: Employees' occupational safety and health are positively and significantly impacted by organizational culture.
- H2: The workplace has a positive and significant impact on employees' occupational safety and health.
- H3: Employees' occupational safety and health are positively and significantly impacted by their work motivation.
- H4: Employee motivation is positively and significantly impacted by organizational culture.
- H5: Employee motivation is positively and significantly influenced by the workplace.
- H6: Through employee motivation, organizational culture has a positive and considerable impact on occupational safety and health.

H7: Employee motivation at work has a favorable and considerable impact on occupational safety and health.

III. STUDY METHODS

In this study, quantitative research methods were employed. Explicit, methodical, planned, and organized needs that are stated at the outset and used to create the research design are what constitute quantitative research. This study used a survey as its primary technique of data collection, which involves developing a list of questions that are then distributed to respondents as a questionnaire. Organizational culture (X1), work environment (X2), motivation at work (Z), and security at work (Y) are the four Xs. Also serving as a mediating variable is the motivational variable (Z) mentioned above. The sample population of this study consists of 50 employees from PT Manunggal Jaya Makmur who have permanent employment status. A non-probability sampling strategy is used in this investigation. A form of sampling called saturated sampling or census involves choosing or taking all members of the population (Kasmir, 2022).

Internal company documents are used as both quantitative primary data and qualitative secondary data. The Component Based Structural Model or Variance was utilized for analysis, and Partial Least Square (Smart-PLS) version 3.0 was employed for data processing.

IV. CONCLUSION AND RESULTS

A. Testing of the measurement model's outer model

The measurement model's or outer model's test findings are used to gauge the validity and dependability of the model. The convergent and discriminant validity of the indicators as well as the composite reliability of the indicator block were used to evaluate the outer model with reflexive indicators. The outcomes of the AVE convergent test are displayed in the table below:

Table 2. Value for Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Variable	AVE Value
Culture of the company (X1)	0.607
Environment at work (X2)	0.666
Motivation at work (Z)	0.619
Safety and health at work (Y)	0.659

Source: PLS 2023 output

Table 2 above demonstrates the PLS results, which indicate that all variables have an AVE value > 0.5. Each variable in the study is thus valid or satisfies convergent validity requirements.

Table 3. Results of the discriminant validity test (Fornell Lacker Criteria)

	Corporate culture	Safety and health at work	Environment at work	Motivation at work
Corporate culture	0.779			
Safety and health at work	0.642	0.816		
Environment at work	0.426	0.805	0.787	
Motivation at work	0.574	0.803	0.636	0.812

Source: PLS 2023 output

According to Table 3, each intended construct's loading value is higher than that of the other constructions. As can be observed, the correlation variable for organizational culture has a loading value of 0.779, which is higher than the correlation value for the variable with other variables. The Fornell-Lacker Criterion test has thus met the criterion for discriminant validity.

Table 4. Results of the Composite Reliability Test and Cronbach's Alpha

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Culture of the company (X1)	0.909	0.925
Environment at work (X2)	0.944	0.951
Motivation at work (Z)	0.895	0.920
Safety and health at work (Y)	0.954	0.960

Source: PLS 2023 output

All latent variable values have a Composite Reliability value of less than 0.7, according to Table 4's findings from the Composite Reliability test. All latent variable values have a Cronbach's Alpha value of less than 0.7, according to the findings of the Cronbach's Alpha test. The occupational safety and health variable has the greatest composite reliability score (0.960), and the work motivation variable has the lowest (0.920).

According to the test findings for Cronbach's Alpha, the variable measuring workplace safety and health has the highest value at 0.954 and the variable measuring job motivation has the lowest value at 0.895. The construct has strong reliability, or the questionnaire utilized as a research tool is consistent and dependable based on these findings (Ghozali, 2015).

B. Evaluation of the Inner Model for Measurement

To analyze the structural model (inner model) or test the hypothesis in this study by analyzing the R2, Predictive Relevance (Q2), and Overall Structural Model Validation (GoF) values.

Table 5. Results of the R-Square Calculation (R2)

Variable	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Motivation at work (Z)	0.516	0.495
Safety and health at work (Y)	0.824	0.813

Source: PLS 2023 output

It is evident from Table 5 above that the Work Motivation (Z) construct's R Square value (R2) is 0.516. These findings suggest that the exogenous variables Organizational Culture (X1) and Work Environment (X2) may explain 51.6% of the endogenous variable Work Motivation (Z), while other exogenous variables can explain the remaining 48.4%. At the same time, exogenous variables such as organizational culture (X1), work environment (X2), and motivation (Z) can account for 82.4% of the construct of occupational safety and health (Y). While other external factors can account for the remaining 17.6%.

C. Indicator of Goodness of Fit (GoF)

According to Ghozali and Latan (2015), the criteria for the GoF value are 0.10 for a small GoF, 0.25 for a medium GoF, and 0.36 for a high GoF. The following formula must be used to manually search for the GoF value in PLS.

$$GoF = \sqrt{AVE \times R^2}$$

$$(0.607 + 0.666 + 0.619 + 0.659)/4 = 0.637 \text{ is the average AVE value.}$$

$$\text{Average } R^2 \text{ value is equal to } 0.67 \text{ } (0.516 + 0.824)/2.$$

$$GoF = \sqrt{0.637 \times 0.67} = \sqrt{0.426} = 0.653$$

The Goodness of Fit Index (GoF) calculation results show a value of 0.653. These findings lead to the conclusion that the measurement model's (outer model) and structural model's (inner model) combined performance is good since the Goodness of Fit Index (GoF) value is more than 0.36 (GoF big scale).

D. Possibility Development

If the T-table significance is higher than 1.98 at a significance threshold of 5% (alpha = 0.05), the estimated value of the route coefficient is considered significant. The research hypothesis can be concluded after reviewing the data that was gathered. If the T-statistic value is higher than the T table used to test the research hypothesis in this study, the research hypothesis is considered accepted.

Table 6. Results of Hypothesis Testing

	Original Sample (O)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Information
Corporate culture (X1) -> Safety and health at work (Y)	0.228	0.077	2.969	0.003	Significant Positive
Corporate culture (X1) -> Motivation at work (Z)	0.370	0.085	4.350	0.000	Significant Positive
Environment at work (X2) -> Safety and health at work (Y)	0.470	0.095	4.955	0.000	Significant Positive
Environment at work (X2) -> Motivation at work (Z)	0.478	0.076	6.262	0.000	Significant Positive
Motivation at work (Z) -> Safety and health at work (Y)	0.373	0.109	3.432	0.001	Significant Positive

Source: PLS 2023 output

Table 7. Results of Indirect Effect Value

	Original Sample (O)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Information
Corporate culture (X1) -> Motivation at work (Z) -> Safety and health at work (Y)	0.138	0.052	2.656	0.008	Significant Positive
Environment at work (X2) -> Motivation at work (Z) -> Safety and health at work (Y)	0.178	0.061	2.912	0.004	Significant Positive

Source: PLS 2023 output

The following figure shows the outcomes of evaluating the study hypothesis :

Image 2. Results of Hypothesis Testing

E. Discussion

The route coefficient value is 0.228, the t-statistic value is 2,969 > 1.98, and the P-Values = 0.003 = 0.05 are all known based on Table 6. This indicates that the variable for organizational culture (X1) has a favorable and significant impact on the variable for occupational safety and health (Y). Therefore, the study's hypothesis (H1) that "Organizational Culture (X1) Has a Positive and Significant Effect on Occupational Safety and Health (Y)" is accepted. The findings of studies by Setyowidodo (2022), Erlina (2017), and Nielsen (2014), which claim that organizational culture can affect employee safety and health, are consistent with this.

According to Table 6, the path coefficient value is 0.370, the t-statistic value is 4,350 > 1,988, and the P-Values are 0.000 = 0.05. It follows that the Work Motivation variable (Z) is significantly and favorably impacted by the Organizational Culture variable (X1) in this relationship. Therefore, the study's hypothesis (H2) that "Organizational Culture (X1) Has a Positive and Significant Effect on Work Motivation (Z)" is accepted. The findings of study by Alamsyah (2023), Lathiifa (2023), and Noniulpa (2023), which claim that corporate culture might affect employee motivation, are consistent with this.

The values of the path coefficient (0.470), the t-statistic (4,955 > 1.98), and the P-Values (0.000 = 0.05) are known based on Table 6. This indicates that Occupational Safety and Health (Y) is positively and significantly impacted by the

Work Environment variable (X2). Thus, the study's hypothesis (H3) that "Work Environment (X2) on Occupational Safety and Health (Y)" is true is accepted. This is consistent with the findings of M's investigation. According to Syariffudin and Parma (2020), the workplace environment can have an impact on occupational safety and health.

The path coefficient value is 0.478, the t-statistic value is $6,262 > 1.98$, and the P-Values are $0.000 = 0.05$, according to Table 6. This indicates that Work Motivation (Z) is positively and significantly influenced by the Work Environment variable (X2). Thus, the study's hypothesis (H4) that "Work Environment (X2) on Work Motivation (Z)" is true is accepted. According to studies by Alamsyah (2023), Cahyaningsih (2023), Lathiiifa (2023), and Yunitashari (2023), the workplace atmosphere might have an impact on employees' motivation to do their best work.

The route coefficient value is 0.373, the t-statistic value is $3,432 > 1.98$, and the P-Values = $0.000 = 0.05$ are all known based on Table 6. Therefore, Occupational Safety and Health (Y) is positively and significantly impacted by the variable Work Motivation (Z). Therefore, the study's hypothesis (H5) that "Work Motivation (Z) on Occupational Safety and Health (K3) (Y)" is accepted. The findings of studies by Nyoman Rai (2015) and Hedianto, Mukzam, and Iqbal (2014), which found that job motivation can impact occupational safety and health (K3), are consistent with this.

The route coefficient value is 0.138, the t-statistic value is $2.656 > 1.98$, and the P-Values = $0.010 = 0.05$ are all known based on Table 7. This indicates that the Employee Motivation (Z) variable is a mediator between the Organizational Culture (X1) variable and the Occupational Safety and Health (Y) variable. Therefore, the study's hypothesis (H6) that "Organizational Culture (X1) has a positive and significant effect on the Occupational Safety and Health variable (Y), which is mediated by Employee Motivation (Z)" is accepted. Ikiningtyas, Al Musadieg, and Prasetya's (2019) research findings indicating workplace safety and health having a unidirectional influence on work motivation also support this. The findings of Rizkiono's research from 2017 demonstrate that the impact of work motivation as an intervening variable has a favorable influence on the relationship between employee performance and occupational safety and health.

The route coefficient value is 0.178, the t-statistic value is $2.912 > 1.98$, and the P-Values = $0.009 = 0.05$ are all known based on Table 7. The Occupational Safety and Health (K3) variable (Y) is influenced positively and significantly by the Work Environment (X2) variable (X2), which is mediated by Employee Motivation (Z). Therefore, the study's hypothesis (H7) that "Work Environment (X2) has a positive and significant effect on the Occupational Safety and Health (K3) (Y) variable, mediated by Employee Motivation (Z)" is accepted. Ikiningtyas, Al Musadieg, and Prasetya's (2019) research findings indicating workplace safety and health can impact job motivation also support this. Suyatno & Rohwiyati's research findings from 2021

demonstrate that motivation can act as a mediator between the impact of the workplace environment and employee performance. According to Mattajang, Nurwulandari, and Hardin's research findings from the year 2022, the motivating variable has the greatest direct impact on employee performance, followed by the variables related to workplace safety and health, work environment, and work discipline. The findings of Andan's (2018) study demonstrate that motivation might mediate the link between the impact of workplace safety and health and worker productivity.

V. CONCLUSION

The study's findings suggest that PT Manunggal Jaya Makmur's organizational culture and workplace environment have an impact on employee motivation. PT Manunggal Jaya Makmur has discovered as a result that highly motivated teams achieve the best results. At PT Manunggal Jaya Makmur, organizational culture and a positive work environment can also have an impact on occupational safety and health (K3), namely by lowering the likelihood of workplace accidents. Additionally, the relationship between organizational culture and the work environment on occupational safety and health (K3) at PT Manunggal Jaya Makmur is known to be mediated by the mediating variable, namely work motivation.

By granting freedom rather than creating distance, managers and other employees are supposed to establish a strong rapport. It is important to think about the social lives of older workers as well as maintaining a professional work environment. To ensure the financial stability of its employees when they retire, company management specifically needs to take pension funds into consideration. Employers can raise employee incentive to improve OHS and lower the risk of workplace accidents by providing job training programs for staff members before, during, and after work. Some of these research variables may be used in subsequent studies, and it is recommended to expand the number of variables by redefining the variables related to employee development, education, occupational safety and health (K3), and training standards. so that it will compare the findings of this study with those of other related studies.

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